

A Prospective Analysis of Hematological Parameters in Neonatal Sepsis**Tejendra Kumar Jha¹, Deepak Kumar², Rajnish Chandra Mishra³**¹Senior Resident, Department of Paediatrics, Jannayak Karpuri Thakur Medical College & Hospital, Madhepura, Bihar, India²Specialist Medical Officer (Paediatrics), Sub Divisional Hospital, Pupri, Sitamarhi, Bihar, India³H.O.D., Department of Paediatrics & Neonatology, Jannayak Karpuri Thakur Medical College & Hospital, Madhepura, Bihar, India

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Abstract:

Neonatal sepsis remains a major cause of morbidity and mortality in newborns, necessitating early and accurate diagnosis. This prospective study evaluated the hematological parameters of 120 neonates suspected of sepsis, including white blood cell count, absolute neutrophil count, immature to total neutrophil ratio, and platelet count. The findings revealed significant elevations in white blood cell and neutrophil counts, the I/T ratio, and a marked decrease in platelet count in septic neonates compared to controls. Elevated I/T ratio and thrombocytopenia were significant predictors of poor outcomes, emphasizing their diagnostic and prognostic utility. These results highlight the importance of routine hematological monitoring for timely intervention in neonatal sepsis, potentially improving clinical outcomes and reducing mortality. Keywords: neonatal sepsis, hematological parameters, early diagnosis, thrombocytopenia.

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Introduction

Neonatal sepsis is a significant cause of morbidity and mortality in newborns, especially in developing countries. It is characterized by a systemic inflammatory response to infection and can lead to severe complications if not diagnosed and treated promptly [1,2]. Early identification and management of neonatal sepsis are crucial to improving clinical outcomes. Hematological parameters, including white blood cell count, platelet count, and various other blood indices, play a vital role in the early detection and monitoring of sepsis in neonates [3].

Neonatal sepsis can be classified into early-onset sepsis (EOS), occurring within the first 72 hours of life, and late-onset sepsis (LOS), which occurs after 72 hours [4]. The etiology of neonatal sepsis varies, with common pathogens including Group B Streptococcus, Escherichia coli, and other Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacteria. The clinical presentation of sepsis in neonates can be subtle and non-specific, making it challenging to diagnose based solely on clinical symptoms [5].

Hematological parameters provide valuable information that can assist in the early detection of sepsis. These parameters include complete blood count (CBC), neutrophil count, immature to total neutrophil ratio (I/T ratio), and platelet count [6]. Changes in these parameters can indicate the presence of an infection and the body's response to

it. For example, an elevated white blood cell count or an increased I/T ratio may suggest an ongoing infection, while thrombocytopenia can be a marker of severe sepsis or disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC) [7].

This prospective study aims to evaluate the changes in hematological parameters in neonates diagnosed with sepsis and to assess their diagnostic and prognostic value. By understanding the patterns and significance of these parameters, clinicians can improve the early diagnosis and management of neonatal sepsis, ultimately reducing the associated morbidity and mortality.

Methodology

Study Design: This prospective study was conducted to evaluate hematological parameters in neonates diagnosed with sepsis. The study was carried out over a period leading up to March 2024. The research was designed to include a diverse sample of neonates presenting with clinical signs of sepsis in a neonatal intensive care unit (NICU).

Study Population: Neonates admitted to the NICU with suspected sepsis were included in the study. The inclusion criteria were:

- Neonates of both genders, aged 0-28 days
- Clinical signs and symptoms suggestive of sepsis, such as temperature instability,

respiratory distress, lethargy, poor feeding, and abnormal blood glucose levels

- Positive blood culture or strong clinical suspicion based on risk factors and clinical presentation

Exclusion Criteria Included:

- Neonates with congenital anomalies or other underlying conditions that could affect hematological parameters.
- Neonates receiving treatment for other significant infections or conditions.

Sample Size: The sample size was determined based on the prevalence of neonatal sepsis in the NICU and the statistical power required to detect significant differences in hematological parameters. A minimum of 100 neonates meeting the inclusion criteria were enrolled in the study to ensure robust and reliable results.

Data Collection

Data collection was performed systematically to maintain accuracy and consistency. The following steps were involved:

1. **Baseline Data Collection:** Upon admission, demographic and clinical data were recorded, including gestational age, birth weight, gender, Apgar scores, and maternal history.
2. **Hematological Analysis:** Blood samples were collected from each neonate when suspected sepsis was diagnosed. Complete blood count (CBC), including white blood cell count, neutrophil count, immature to total neutrophil ratio (I/T ratio), and platelet count, were measured using standard laboratory techniques.
3. **Follow-Up:** Repeat hematological parameters were measured at 24-, 48-, and 72-hours post-diagnosis to monitor changes over time. Additional samples were taken if clinically indicated.
4. **Microbiological Analysis:** Blood cultures were performed to identify the causative pathogens and confirm sepsis diagnosis.
5. **Outcome Assessment:** Clinical outcomes, including recovery, complications, and mortality, were documented. The response to antibiotic therapy and any adverse events were also recorded.

Statistical Analysis: The collected data were analyzed using appropriate statistical methods to determine the significance of changes in hematological parameters. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize baseline characteristics and hematological values. Comparative analysis between septic and non-septic neonates was performed using t-tests or non-parametric equivalents, as appropriate. Logistic regression

analysis was conducted to assess the prognostic value of hematological parameters in predicting outcomes.

Results

A total of 120 neonates suspected of having sepsis were enrolled in the study, with an even distribution between genders (60 males and 60 females). The mean gestational age was 38.2 weeks (range 30-42 weeks), and the average birth weight was 2.8 kg (range 1.5-4.0 kg). Most neonates presented with symptoms within the first week of life, with 70 cases categorized as early-onset sepsis (EOS) and 50 as late-onset sepsis (LOS).

Hematological Parameters

The following hematological parameters were evaluated: white blood cell (WBC) count, absolute neutrophil count (ANC), immature to total neutrophil ratio (I/T ratio), and platelet count.

1. White Blood Cell Count

- The mean WBC count in septic neonates was significantly higher at the time of diagnosis (18,500 cells/mm³) compared to the non-septic control group (12,000 cells/mm³) ($p < 0.05$).
- EOS cases had a slightly higher mean WBC count (19,200 cells/mm³) than LOS cases (17,500 cells/mm³).

2. Absolute Neutrophil Count

- The mean ANC was also elevated in septic neonates (10,200 cells/mm³) compared to controls (7,500 cells/mm³) ($p < 0.05$).
- EOS cases exhibited a mean ANC of 10,800 cells/mm³, while LOS cases had a mean of 9,600 cells/mm³.

3. Immature to Total Neutrophil Ratio

- The mean I/T ratio in septic neonates was significantly higher (0.25) compared to the control group (0.15) ($p < 0.05$).
- The I/T ratio was elevated in both EOS (0.26) and LOS (0.24) cases, with no significant difference between the two groups.

4. Platelet Count

- Septic neonates had a significantly lower mean platelet count (120,000 cells/mm³) compared to controls (250,000 cells/mm³) ($p < 0.05$).
- Thrombocytopenia (platelet count $< 150,000$ cells/mm³) was observed in 60% of septic neonates, with a higher incidence in EOS (65%) compared to LOS (55%).

Microbiological Analysis: Blood cultures confirmed the presence of bacterial pathogens in 70% of the cases. The most common pathogens identified were:

- Group B Streptococcus (35%)
- Escherichia coli (25%)
- Staphylococcus aureus (15%)

- Klebsiella pneumoniae (10%)
- Other Gram-negative bacteria (15%)

Clinical Outcomes

- Recovery: 75% of the septic neonates showed clinical improvement and recovery with appropriate antibiotic therapy.
- Complications: 15% of the septic neonates developed complications such as disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC), meningitis, or persistent pulmonary hypertension.
- Mortality: The mortality rate was 10%, with higher rates observed in EOS cases (12%) compared to LOS cases (8%).

Prognostic Value of Hematological Parameters:
 Logistic regression analysis demonstrated that an

elevated I/T ratio ($p < 0.01$) and thrombocytopenia ($p < 0.05$) were significant predictors of poor clinical outcomes in neonatal sepsis. Neonates with an I/T ratio > 0.25 and platelet count $< 100,000$ cells/mm³ had a higher risk of developing severe complications or mortality.

The study highlighted the importance of hematological parameters in the early diagnosis and prognosis of neonatal sepsis. Elevated WBC count, ANC, I/T ratio, and decreased platelet count were significantly associated with sepsis in neonates. These findings underscore the need for prompt and accurate hematological evaluation in suspected cases of neonatal sepsis to improve clinical outcomes and reduce mortality.

	Group	WBC Count (cells/mm ³)	p-value	
1	Septic Neonates	18500	< 0.05	
2	Control Group	12000	< 0.05	
3	EOS Cases	19200	< 0.05	
4	LOS Cases	17500	< 0.05	

	Group	Absolute Neutrophil	p-value	
1	Septic Neonates	10200	< 0.05	
2	Control Group	7500	< 0.05	
3	EOS Cases	10800	< 0.05	
4	LOS Cases	9600	< 0.05	

	Group	I/T Ratio	p-value	
1	Septic Neonates	0.25	< 0.05	
2	Control Group	0.15	< 0.05	
3	EOS Cases	0.26	< 0.05	
4	LOS Cases	0.24	< 0.05	

	Group	Platelet Count (cells/	p-value	
1	Septic Neonates	120000	< 0.05	
2	Control Group	250000	< 0.05	

Discussion

The findings of this study underscore the critical role of hematological parameters in the early diagnosis and management of neonatal sepsis. Elevated white blood cell (WBC) counts and absolute neutrophil counts (ANC) were observed in septic neonates compared to the control group, indicating a robust inflammatory response to infection. These parameters were particularly elevated in cases of early-onset sepsis (EOS) compared to late-onset sepsis (LOS), suggesting that the timing of infection may influence the degree of hematological response [8,9].

The immature to total neutrophil ratio (I/T ratio) was significantly higher in septic neonates, with a mean value of 0.25, compared to 0.15 in the control group. This ratio is a well-known marker of neonatal sepsis and its elevation reinforces its diagnostic value. The slight difference between EOS and LOS cases (0.26 vs. 0.24) indicates that while the I/T ratio is a reliable indicator of sepsis, it may not distinctly differentiate between the onset times of sepsis [10,11].

Thrombocytopenia, or reduced platelet count, was markedly prevalent in septic neonates, with an average count of 120,000 cells/mm³ compared to

250,000 cells/mm³ in the control group. This significant drop in platelet count is a concerning indicator, often associated with severe sepsis and disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC). The higher incidence of thrombocytopenia in EOS cases (65%) compared to LOS cases (55%) may reflect a more severe inflammatory response or a different pathophysiological mechanism in early-onset infections [12,13].

Microbiological analysis revealed that Group B Streptococcus and Escherichia coli were the predominant pathogens, aligning with existing literature on the common etiological agents in neonatal sepsis. The identification of these pathogens emphasizes the need for targeted antibiotic therapy, which is crucial for effective management and improving outcomes [14,15].

The clinical outcomes further highlight the importance of early diagnosis and intervention. The majority of septic neonates showed clinical improvement with appropriate antibiotic therapy, yet a notable percentage developed complications such as DIC, meningitis, or persistent pulmonary hypertension. The mortality rate of 10% among septic neonates underscores the severity of the

condition, with higher mortality observed in EOS cases [16].

Logistic regression analysis demonstrated that an elevated I/T ratio and thrombocytopenia were significant predictors of poor clinical outcomes, reinforcing their prognostic value. These findings suggest that close monitoring of these parameters can help identify neonates at higher risk for complications and mortality, allowing for timely and more aggressive therapeutic interventions. This study highlights the significant diagnostic and prognostic value of hematological parameters in neonatal sepsis [17,18]. Elevated WBC count, ANC, I/T ratio, and decreased platelet count are critical markers that can aid in the early detection and effective management of sepsis in neonates. These findings advocate for routine hematological monitoring in suspected cases of neonatal sepsis to improve clinical outcomes and reduce associated morbidity and mortality [19,20].

Conclusion

This prospective study demonstrates the critical importance of hematological parameters in the early diagnosis and management of neonatal sepsis. Elevated white blood cell count, absolute neutrophil count, and immature to total neutrophil ratio, alongside decreased platelet count, were significantly associated with septic neonates, highlighting their diagnostic and prognostic value. These findings underscore the necessity for routine and vigilant hematological monitoring in neonates with suspected sepsis, enabling timely and effective intervention. By leveraging these parameters, clinicians can improve the outcomes for neonates, reducing the morbidity and mortality associated with this severe condition.

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